

Survey on Users Ranking Pattern based Trust Model Regularization in Product Recommendation

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ABSTRACT

It is recommended to trust SVD, a trust-based matrix decomposition technique to provide advice. Trust SVD is integrated into the recommendation model to reduce data sparsity and cold start issues and their recommended performance degradation. The proposed system is a new framework for social trust data from four real-world datasets, which indicates that not only the explicit and implicit impact of ratings and trust should be considered in the recommendation model. Trust SVD extends to SVD ++, using the explicit and implicit impact of rated projects by further combining the explicit and implicit impact of trust and trust users on active user project predictions. Trust SVD to achieve better accuracy than other recommended technology methods. This method is overcome by introducing a frequency-based algorithm to reduce the error rate and avoid language problems, thereby improving the accuracy of the recommendation.

Keywords: Spectral line, local spectral component decomposition, denoising, hyper spectral image

I. INTRODUCTION

The recommendation system helps the user to potentially reduce the reliance on search algorithms by improving the discoverability of the items because they connect related information to users who may be hard to find. The recommendation system is mainly used in many fields such as e-commerce, marketing, financial services, and personalized holidays, etc. The user experience is enhanced by providing personalized recommendations that focus on user

tastes and needs, thereby improving profitability. The recommended technologies are roughly divided into content-based filtering technologies, collaborative filtering technologies, and hybrid recommendation systems. The recommendation system is used to recommend resources that the user may be interested in by mining user interests and/or preferences. The proposed system matches the user database with the items available in the project database and makes suggestions accordingly. The recommendation system provides the user with personalization Help and information about the product or service to support its decision-making process. Personalization involves adapting to each user's personal needs, interests, and preferences. Most e-commerce sites such as Myntra.com and social networking sites such as facebook.com have such a recommendation system. These systems serve two important tasks (1), helping users to process excess information by providing users with appropriate advice (2), and helping users to earn more profits by selling more products. Recommended systems recommend "people" (partners, consultants, friends, etc.) or "things" (movies, songs, books, etc.). The recommendation system usually creates a recommendation list in one of two ways through collaboration or content-based filtering. Collaborative filtering relies on collecting and analyzing a large amount of information about user behavior, activities, and predicting what the user will like based on similarities with other users. The content-based filtering method is based on the project's description and the user's preferred profile.

Figure 1.1: Types of recommender systems

Content-based filtering strategy: Use user preference profiles and project description information about historical transactions. For example, the content filtering music recommendation system may consider using attributes of the user's favorite songs, such as music genres, singers, musicians, beats, etc., and they may recommend other songs that may be of interest to the user based on the song. Collecting data from external sources is necessary for these potentially challenging systems. Collaborative Filtering (CF) strategy: On the other hand, it completely relies on the past behavior demonstrated by users. CF usually outperforms content-based filtering in terms of content. Except for the cold start situation, where the product or user is relatively new, CF has failed to provide meaningful suggestions. The second problem faced by CF is sparse data because users typically only evaluate a small portion of the millions of available projects. Third, these systems are difficult to scale because millions of users and millions of products make task calculation very expensive.

CF technology is further classified as a neighborhood method and a latent factor model. Because the neighborhood method calculates the relationship between items or the relationship between the user and the user to provide suggestions, the latent factor model determines the characteristics of the item and the user on multiple factors based on the evaluation model. User relationships can be described in terms of social trust networks based on online (ie, trust) relationships and offline (trust-like) relationships between users. The proposed trust SVD is a trust-based matrix decomposition technique for recommendation. Trust SVD integrates multiple sources of information into the recommendation model to reduce data sparsity and cold-start problems and their recommended performance degradation. The analysis of social trust data from four real-world datasets shows that not only the explicit impact of

ratings and trust should be considered in the recommendation model, but also implicit impacts should be considered. Therefore, the trust SVD builds on the most advanced recommendation algorithm SVD ++ (which uses the explicit and implicit impact of the evaluation project), further combining the project of the user who trusts and trusts the user explicitly and implicitly to influence the activity. . The proposed technology is the first to extend SVD++ with social trust information. The title of the proposed system is "Regularization of trust models based on user ranking models in product recommendations." The proposed system is designed to recommend product items based on user trust and user ratings. It is a new system based on project conceptual model and NLP (Non-Language Processing) linguistics tool to improve the trust value. The FB mining algorithm can be used to extract concept frequencies and can be added to the project concept matrix. It can also be considered readability, integrity, emotions and other language features to build scores. Both of these parameters will improve the ranking process of the recommendation system.

Figure 2.2: Basic Block Diagram

These relationships can strongly and weakly influence users' opinions. Hybrid recommendation mode: Combines content-based filtering with CF technology sequencing. Neighbor Technology: The recommendation system can use trusted neighbors because it can improve the accuracy of the recommendation system, coverage, and system performance. This method works well when the sparsely distributed rating data is sparse, but when the ratings are diversified, most of the strategies used in this paper do not apply. It shows us how to generate a recommendation, and the trustworthy neighbor's score is merged. Latent factorization method: Combining the neighborhood and latent factorization models together to provide improved accuracy, thereby complementing each other through the use of different levels of neighborhood and latent factor models to

improve system performance. It also provides an effective global optimization scheme, but it has not been tested with large data sets that are related to implicit feedback. It integrates implicit user feedback into the neighborhood model and latent factor model (svd).

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The problem definition is trust and trust. If the relationship does not fully contribute to the quality of the recommendation system, then the conceptual frequency and the quality of the scoring usually degrade the recommendation system. The recommendation system is critical to the success of many online applications/services because they play an important role in tailoring these applications to the specific needs or preferences of users. Although they are becoming more and more popular, in general, the recommendation system suffers from sparse data and cold start problems. In order to alleviate these problems, people have increased their interest in using social information and evaluation data such as trust relationships between users in recent years to improve the performance of the recommendation system. The main motivation for using trust information in the recommendation process comes from the observation that the ideas that we come in contact with and the ideas that we choose to generate are strongly influenced by our social context. However, in the large-scale user group, there is also a trust relationship between users in addition to the trust relationship. For example, in epinions, the concepts of individuals "trusted networks" and individuals "blocked lists" allow users to classify their friends as trusted and untrusted friends, respectively, based on the quality of the reviews. Therefore, including this will be interesting.

The same is true for new sources of recommended information. The potential for clear inclusion of a mistrust relationship is almost undetected compared to the inclusion of trust information in the proposal that is flourishing. In this paper, we propose a matrix decomposition-based model to recommend a social rating network that correctly combines trust and distrust, designed to improve the quality of recommendations and reduce data sparsity and cold-start user issues. through experiments. In the epinions dataset, the new algorithm outperforms the standard trust enhanced or incompatible enhanced counterparts in terms of accuracy, demonstrating positive results:

Clear non-trust information can be included in the recommendation system. In a social rating network, users can tag (add) other users as trusted friends to form a social network. Trust is not symmetric. For example, user u_1 trusts u_3 , but u_3 does not specify user u_1 as trusted. In addition, the user can use a plurality of rating values to score a group of items, such as integers from 1 to 5. These items can be products, movies, music of interest. The recommendation problem in this work is to predict the user's rating of unknown items, for example, user u_3 will give the value of item i based on the user item rating matrix and the user user trust matrix.

Other recognized recommendation issues include, for example, the top N recommendation hypothesis recommendation system includes users and n items. Let the user project score matrix (where each entry i represents the score given by user u for item i). For the sake of clarity save symbols u for users and keep sy for the project. Since the user only evaluates a small number of items, the scoring matrix R is only partially observed and is usually very sparse. Let user u evaluate a set of items. Let p_u and q_i be the d -dimensional latent feature vectors of user u and item i , respectively. The essence of matrix decomposition is to find two low rank matrices: user characteristic matrix m and item characteristic matrix, which can fully recover the nominal matrix R , where P is the transpose of matrix P . The basic assumption is that users and projects can be characterized by a small number of features. Thus, the score for item u of user u may be predicted from the inner product of the user-specific vector and the item-specific vector. In this regard, the main task of the proposal is to predict the rating as close as possible to the actual situation. Formally, learn user and project features. It is now assumed that the social network is represented by a graph G , where V includes a set of m nodes (users), and E represents a directed trust relationship between users. Use the adjacency matrix $T_{,m}$ to describe the structure of the edge E , where v represents the range v you trust. In general, only the binary value is used to indicate that the user trusts user v for a non-trust relationship. Similar to the user item scoring matrix R , the trust matrix T is also very sparse in the d -dimensional latent feature vector of truster u and trustee v , respectively. Limit the active users in the trust and restriction matrix in the trust matrix to share the same user feature space so that they are bridged together. Therefore, the truster feature matrix m and the trustee feature matrix. The low-rank matrix

approximation restores the trust matrix by $T_P > W$. Therefore, the trust relationship can be predicted through the internal products of the truster specific vector and the trustee specific vector. The matrices P and w can be learned by minimizing the following loss functions: where u is the set of users that user u trusts, ie the set of outgoing trusted users. In summary, the two kinds of information are linked together by mapping the grading matrix and the trust matrix to the same d -dimensional space. Collaborative filtering (CF) is one of the most popular techniques for implementing recommendation systems. The idea of CF is that in the past there might be users with similar preferences. In the future benefit the same items (eg movies, music, books, etc.). In addition to project recommendations in the fields of image processing and bioinformatics, CF has also been applied to tasks. However, CF suffers from two well-known problems, sparse data and cold start. The former problem means that users usually only score a small number of items, while the latter indicates that new users only give a few ratings to cold-start users. Both of these problems severely reduce the efficiency of the recommendation system in modeling user preferences, and thus severely reduce the accuracy of user ratings for predicting unknown items. The CF method is better than the memory-based method. These methods further normalize user-specific feature vectors through the phenomenon in which friends often interact with each other in recommendation projects.

However, even the best performance of the latest work report is not as good as the other most advanced models based solely on user project ratings. Root mean squared error (RMSE), while the user project baseline performance can be realized. The possible explanation for RMSE is that these trust-based models over-concern the utility of user trust, but neglect the impact of project rating itself. To investigate this phenomenon, empirical trust analysis was conducted based on four real-world data. Three important opinions have emerged. First, trust information is also scarce, but it is complementary to rating information. Therefore, paying too much attention to any kind of information can only gain marginal revenue in terms of forecast accuracy. Second, users are strongly related to their outgoing trusted neighbors (ie, trustees), and they have a weak positive correlation with their trusted neighbors (eg, friends). Then postpone the definition of trust. The third observation further shows that there are similar conclusions with

the upcoming trusted neighbors (ie trustees). This means that existing trust-based models may not work if there is only a trust relationship. Given that there are few trust networks, it is better to have a more general trust-based model that can use trust and trust relationships well. These observations motivate us to consider the explicit and implicit effects of project ratings and user trust in a unified trust-based model. The impact can be clear - the true value of ratings and trust - or implicit - who evaluates what (for rating) and who believes (for trust). The implicit impact of ratings has proven to be useful for providing accurate advice, and implicit trust can also provide added value over explicit trust. The technique used in this article is collaborative filtering of product recommendations. Collaborative Filtering (CF): One of the most popular techniques for implementing a recommendation system. The idea behind CF is that users with similar preferences in the past may be inclined to the same items (eg, music, books, etc.) in the future. The disadvantage is sparse data. If the project is more than the number of users, it is difficult to find user rating items and problems arise in advance. Web-based filtering techniques can recommend new items and no user rating. This method is based on the vand user profile is used to indicate the user's favorite project type. Content-based suggestion steps describe what items may be recommended. Create a user profile that describes the types of items the user likes and compare the items with the user profile to determine what to recommend. This profile is usually created and updated automatically based on feedback. The disadvantage is cold start, lack of information about users and items. The cold boot problem consists of two types: When new users expand the system, they will not be any previous registration list.

The new product is not rated by the user. These two issues have severely reduced the efficiency of the recommendation system and the accuracy of user ratings that predict over-specialization of unknown items. These methods are based on a description of the project and an introduction to user preferences. The items recommended by these algorithms are similar to those items that users have liked or are currently examining. In particular, when multiple candidate items are compared with items previously rated by the user, the best equivalent item is recommended. The root of this method lies in information retrieval and information filtering research. Essentially, these methods use project configuration files that characterize projects within

the system. The system generates a user's content-based configuration file based on the weighted vectors of the project elements. The weights represent the importance of each feature to the user and can be calculated from separately rated content vectors using various techniques. Simple methods use the average of the nominal item vectors, while other sophisticated methods use machine learning techniques such as Bayesian classifiers, cluster analysis, decision trees, and artificial neural networks to estimate the probability that the user will like the item.

P. Massa and P. Avesani [1] proposed a trust recommendation system. The collaborative filtering-based recommendation system suggests user items that they may like. However, due to the data sparsity of the input scoring matrix, the steps to find similar users often fail. This paper proposes replacing it with a trust metric, which is an algorithm that can propagate trust on a trusted network. It also estimates the weight of trust that can be used for place similarity weights. In the first step, we find the neighbors and the second step system predicts the score based on the weighted sum of the scores given by the neighbors for the project. Weights can be derived from user similarity assessments or using trust metrics. The results show that trust is very effective in solving RS weaknesses. The technique used in this article is a model-based approach. These methods further standardize user-specific features through the phenomenon of friend-recommended item efficient stochastic optimization algorithms. In order to solve the optimization problem, the proposed method makes the user's past rating scalable to a large social network. The real-world recommendation process is not reflected in the model that affects the recommended quality. The main disadvantaged user social network is integrated into the recommendation system by decomposing the social trust map. The utility of ratings is not well utilized, and the number and size of social networks are growing, with hundreds of millions of user accounts. Another benefit of these networks.

In this work, they are particularly interested in trust relationships and how they are used to design interfaces. In this article, a website is proposed that uses trust in a Web-based social network to create predictive movie recommendations. When the system is based, when the user's perception of the movie is different from the average, these suggestions are more accurate than other techniques. This technique can be

used as a social network analysis application or as a result of other analysis to help improve all types of collaborative filtering algorithms. Use social trust specifically as the basis of the recommendation system. In order for this technology to succeed, an association must be established between trust and user similarity. In addition, the use of a trust network thus improves the proposed coverage.

However, when the trust network is far from the source user u , the trust between these users and the source users will become quite weak, and their ratings will be noisy and unreliable. Therefore, the score indicated by the user of the neighboring user u must be used. However, in this case, the probability of expressing the item will be very low, and the prediction cannot be calculated. In order to consider adequate ratings without noisy data, a random walk method based on trust and project-based recommendation was proposed. Trust Walker not only considers the score of the target project, but also considers the rating of similar projects. As the length of the walk increases, the score of similar items rather than the score of the target item will increase. The framework contains trust-based and project-based recommendations as a special case. Most traditional recommendation systems do not provide their predictions. The random walk model allows us to perform calculations. Select online information related to a given user. Collaborative filtering is the most popular method of building recommendation systems and has been successfully applied to many applications. However, it cannot provide advice for so-called cold-start users who only evaluate very few projects. Collaboration methods are fairly vulnerable to attacks that spoof user profiles into the database. In the end, these methods do not know what they are suggesting. Trust-based recommendation systems can better handle cold-start users because users simply connect to a trusted network. Trust-based methods are also more robust to fraudulent attacks. On the other hand, the sparsity of user project ratings forces the trust-based approach to consider the ratings of only indirect neighbors with weak trust, which may reduce its accuracy. In order to solve this problem, a random walk model called Trust Walker was proposed. Recommendation based on trusted and project-based collaboration. Trust Walker not only considers the score of the target item, but also considers the score of similar items, and the probability increases with the increase in the length of walking. Another

contribution is that Trust Walker allows us to measure recommendations.

M. Jamali and M. Ester [2] explored a social network recommendation method based on a trust model that uses matrix decomposition techniques. Learn the potential characteristics of users and projects, and predict the ratings that users give to unknown projects in order to consolidate trust spread. The trust-based model focuses on the utility of user trust, but ignores the impact of the project rating itself. Use an empirical trust analysis algorithm. Focusing on various kinds of information may only yield negligible benefits in terms of forecasting accuracy. Users are closely related to their outgoing trusted neighbors (ie trustees). This shows that there are similar conclusions with the upcoming trusted neighbors (ie, thrusters). It is better to have a more general trust-based model that works well with trust and trust relationships. Model-based disadvantages do not consider the explicit and implicit influence of trust at the same time. To further improve the accuracy of the recommendation and to explain the real-world intuition well. A new social MF model was proposed. The social MF model addresses the transitivity problem of trust in social networks by considering trust propagation in the network. Therefore, the feature vector of each direct neighbor depends on the feature vector of his direct neighbor. Even if the user does not express any rating, his feature vector can also be learned through social connections to the social network. Therefore, social MF and cold-start users handle better than existing methods. Collaboration is the most popular method of constructing a recommendation system and has been successfully applied in many applications. However, it cannot make recommendations for so-called cold start users who only evaluate very few items. In addition, these methods do not know what their suggestions are. The trust-based recommendation method assumes that the trust network between users has additional knowledge and can better deal with cold-start users because users simply connect to the trust network. On the other hand, the sparsity of user project ratings forces the trust-based approach to consider the ratings of only indirect neighbors with weak trust, which may reduce its accuracy. Alice, Bob and Joe are similar to Jack on their history (left side of the movie). Now want to recommend a new movie to Jack from the list on the right. According to the past love of Alice, Bob and Joe, the western time "All three like it, but Spider-Man" is only liked by two people. Therefore, Western

countries may have been recommended to Jack for some time. Cold start is a potential problem for any data-driven system, including the recommendation system trying to build a model based on existing information. Since the project (or user) vector does not have enough evaluation items for similar vectors, the algorithm is very low. In the content-based method, the system must be able to match the characteristics of the project with the relevant features of the user, and therefore, needs to be constructed. A detailed model of user preferences and preferences, therefore, in the absence of a detailed model of user preferences and preferences, the system will not be able to match the appropriate items, thereby appreciating the user. Recommended system users. Similar preferences to active users, and recommendations for like-minded users (as well as items that active users haven't seen yet). Due to the cold start problem, this method will not be able to consider items that have not been evaluated by the system. Cold start problems can be mitigated by applying hybrid methods such as content-based methods and collaboration methods.

Guo Lei et al. [3] proposed a new trust-based method named trust MF. Traditionally, the trust-aware recommendation method using a trust relationship with the recommendation system assumes that there is a single type of trust between users. In fact, this assumption ignores factual trust because social concepts inherently have many aspects. In many types of recommendation systems, users have different trust for different people. In order to solve the above problems, this paper proposes to fuse user category information with the scoring matrix. This paper proposes a probabilistic factor analysis technique for learning multi-level trust relationships by sharing the user's latent feature space. The user's potential feature space in the user category is the same in the scoring matrix. Use a trust-based recommendation model. The trusted SVD algorithm builds on the explicit and implicit impact of user project ratings. The main goal is to generate forecasts. Weighted λ regularization techniques are used to help avoid overfitting model learning. The influence of user trust (including trustees and propellers) on the prediction of ratings for aggressive user disadvantages improves forecasting accuracy.

The potential is extended to a similar relationship of trust. Data Sparse The core of many recommendation systems is a similar user or similar item. Although

there are many algorithms that can solve this problem, almost all algorithms fail when the size of the vector increases and passes some thresholds. When the number of users or items increases, the scoring matrix becomes very sparse. Even if someone can see and rank one thousand of them, the scoring matrix is still very sparse. In these cases, similar users become very numerous and existing algorithms cannot obtain similar users or projects. A common technique for dealing with this problem is to use decomposition methods to reduce the size of the scoring matrix and create a matrix of more relevant and independent features. However, dealing with a very sparse rating matrix remains an open challenge for the recommendation system. The trust attributes in this section describe the characteristics of trust, including transitive asymmetry, context dependencies, and personalization. These attributes are extracted from trust and provide the basis for creating algorithms that leverage trust information. Transitivity is a key attribute of trust. It allows the trust to propagate along the path to reach other users. Based on the transitivity of trust v and v trust w , it can be inferred that u may also trust w to some extent when $T(u;v)$ represents a trust relationship between users u and v and composability. Transitivity describes how trust information is propagated from one user to another through a series of connected users. Commutability describes how users should combine the trust value reception path. There is a way you can use the simplest way to summarize aggregated trust values in their paths and then normalize values based on the range of trust values.

Tong Zhao et al. [4] studied the potential correlation between project labels and trust relationships among users. This paper proposes a topic-based trust-based matrix decomposition (TMF) algorithm based on probability matrix decomposition and uses multi-faceted trust relationships. Only by understanding the characteristics of the projects they choose can we better investigate the interests of users and distinguish their multi-faceted trust. Based on this intuition, the TMF mines topics from the project tags and simultaneously estimates the topic-specific trust relationships between users. Using this topic-specific trust relationship can improve the accuracy of recommendations and solve project cold start problems. This paper presents a factor analysis method based on the decomposition of probability matrix. Solve data sparseness, inaccurate predictions, and accuracy issues by using user social network

information at the same time. In particular, users have almost no ratings. It is linear with the number of observations, which is better than other methods because it performs much better than other methods. Whether or not mistrust information is useful. Do not ignore the spread or spread of information between users. Alice can use it to infer information about Chuck's trust. She then aggregates the trust values from both paths. Asymmetric trust is a subjective and personal relationship between users; therefore, it creates an orientation relationship in social networks. In other words, if uv represents the trust value from user u to user v , it may not necessarily be equal to the trust value from user v to user u . Based on this attribute, user's trust in user v does not guarantee that user v also trusts you to the same extent. Context-dependent trusts are context-sensitive. This means that trusting someone on a topic does not guarantee him belief on other topics. For example, technically trustworthy users may not be trustworthy in astronomy, and there is trust between personalizations. Trust is a personalized property. The amount of trust a person has in another person may vary from person to person. Use this attribute and develop local trust. But in global trust, this is equivalent to the fact that user reputation violates this attribute. In global trust, there is only one trust value per user for all other users in the network

W. Yao et al. [5] propose modeled explicit interactions and implicit interactions with users, and proposed a model to learn the dual role preference recommended by trust consciousness. Users in the trust rating network are associated with two different roles at the same time. They are truster and trustee. "Truster" is a person who trusts others, and "Trustees" is someone who is trusted by others. As a truster, one of them is more likely to be influenced by existing ratings or comments provided by other users' trust. Similarly, as a trustee, contributions (ratings or reviews) will therefore affect other trusted individuals. The user's two roles may have different preferences. For example, for digital product experts who only want to learn, they are more likely to trust a large number of chefs and at the same time be trusted by many consumers of digital products. Therefore, when predicting the user's preferences for an item, it may be reasonable to consider the truster and the trustee's preferences. This article proposes a new social recommendation method. It uses Tulaplais formalization to capture the potential social relationships between users. This is based on

traditional gradient descent optimization. Quasi-Newton algorithm: It is very effective and efficient for social recommendation tasks. Consider the relationship between projects by considering category information. The recommendation system attempts to suggest items (movies, books, music, news, web pages, images, etc.) that may be of interest to the user. Typically, the recommendation system is based on collaborative filtering, which automatically predicts the interests of active users by collecting rating information from other similar users or projects. The basic assumption of collaborative filtering is that active users will like items that similar users like. Based on this simple but effective intuition, collaborative filtering has been widely used in some well-known large-scale commercial systems. However, due to the nature of collaborative filtering, recommendation systems based on this technology suffer from the following inherent weaknesses.

Due to the sparseness of the user project scoring matrix (the density of available scores in business recommendation systems is usually less than that, memory-based collaborative filtering algorithms cannot find similar users because of methods for calculating similarity, such as the Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) or cosine method. The two users have at least some common ground, and almost all memory-based and model-based collaborative filtering algorithms cannot handle users who have never done any evaluation of any project. Trust recommendation and taste among friends and roles can be very easy. Due to the reservation of the company, the traditional recommendation system purely mines the user project scoring matrix to provide suggestions, and these systems give unrealistic output results. The traditional recommendation system assumes users (independent and equally distributed). Ignoring interactions or connections between social users, but the fact is offline, social recommendations happen every day, for example, when you ask a friend to recommend a movie or a good restaurant mainly solicit oral social recommendations. The system gives recommendations with high novelty factors. However, in recommending system recommendations, quality and practicality, and friend suggestions, it is recommended to choose the best. Friends are more qualified to propose good and useful suggestions than traditional ones. To overcome the above-mentioned shortcomings, the social suggestion is a graphical model. based on The intuition that the user's social

network affects personal behavior suggests integrating the user's social networking graphics with the user's item rating matrix in order to provide more accurate and personalized recommendations, which is referred to as social recommendation.

In fact, the methods we developed apply not only to social recommendations but also to many other tasks in social search and information retrieval and data mining. In order to achieve this goal, this paper proposes a method based on probabilistic factor analysis which combines the social network structure with the user project scoring matrix. The two different data resources are connected by sharing the user's latent feature space, that is, the user's latent feature space in the social network structure is the same in the user item scoring matrix. Through factor analysis based on probability matrix decomposition, the potential feature space of low-rank users and the potential feature space of the project are learned to make social recommendations. This method is superior to the most advanced collaborative filtering algorithms, especially when the active user has little or no ratings.

Liu Haifeng et al. [6] proposed a collaborative filtering method CF-TC. In a trust network-based recommendation system, users, trusters, and trustees usually have two roles. Most trust-based methods often use explicit links between trusters and trustees to find similar neighbors for referral. However, there will be implicit associations between users, especially for users with the same role. The proposed CF-TC method mainly includes two parts: (i) mining the implicit correlation between users with the same effect; (ii) applying the mined implicit correlation to the user's rating prediction. First, for each user, a user with the same role as the user is used to build his user representation. Each implicitly related weight is obtained by measuring the cosine similarity between any two users with the same role. In the second step, two variants of CF-TC, CF-TC based on memory and CF-TC based on matrix decomposition are proposed based on computational weights. The technique used in this article is Support Vector Regression. The main purpose is to bridge the gap between trust and user preferences - similarity and use trust information. A latent factor model algorithm is proposed. This establishes a more effective aspect of trust for the referral system. This model is extended by considering other attributes of the trust network, namely trust transitivity. To further improve the

accuracy of the recommendation and to explain the real-world intuition well. The biggest challenge facing the recommendation system is to achieve a high quality of prediction for large-scale sparse data contributed by users. In this paper, a new social recommendation method is proposed, which uses the regularization of Laplace diagrams to capture the potential social relationships between users. Different from the previous methods based on the traditional gradient descent method, the proposed Tunellax regularization social recommendation problem is transformed into a low rank semidefinite programming, which can be effectively solved by the quasi-Newton algorithm. An empirical evaluation of high sparse large-scale datasets, this method is very effective and efficient for social recommendation websites and web applications. The recommendation system screens a large amount of useless information for end users.

The recommendation is not only a major research interest to study, but also a huge business opportunity in practice. In the field of data mining, we are dedicated to recommending related technologies. More importantly, the recommendation system has been deployed in production recommendations. The recommendation system is mainly based on collaborative filtering technology, which uses the information collected from other users to automatically predict the interests of active users. In general, users only score a small portion of the entire project team. Therefore, the big challenge for the recommendation system is how to handle a large number of large-scale datasets that lack entries. Moreover, the traditional recommendation system completely relies on the information of the user's project rating. Recently, a large number of research interests tend to use user connections to improve the quality of predictions. These methods rely on gradient-based optimization of probability matrix decomposition. However, the potential social relationships and tastes between users cannot be effectively captured. Although the ensemble approach mitigates this problem by directly merging the user's preferences with their trustworthy friends' decisions, it involves computationally intensive calculations of fused predictive values. Because the total number of user item ratings is usually very large, the training process can take a lot of time for users with many social relationships. In addition, in order to balance the tastes of users and their friends, weighting parameters must be set based on experience.

G. Adomavicius and A. Tuzhilin, [7] proposed this paper presents an overview of the field of recommender systems and describes the current generation of recommendation methods that are usually classified into the following three main categories: content-based, collaborative and hybrid recommendation approaches. This paper also describes various limitations of current recommendation methods and discusses possible extensions that can improve recommendation capabilities and make recommender systems applicable to an even broader range of applications. These extensions include, among others, an improvement of understanding of users and items, incorporation of the contextual information into the recommendation process, support for multicriteria ratings and a provision of more flexible and less intrusive types of recommendations. Content-based recommendations: The user will be recommended items similar to the ones the user preferred in the past collaborative recommendations: The user will be recommended items that people with similar tastes and preferences liked in the past. Hybrid approaches: These methods combine collaborative and content-based methods. Recommender systems made significant progress over the last decade when numerous content-based, collaborative and hybrid methods were proposed and several "industrial-strength" systems have been developed. However, despite all of these advances, the current generation of recommender systems surveyed in this paper still requires further improvements to make recommendation methods more effective in a broader range of applications. In this paper, reviewed various limitations of the current recommendation methods and discussed possible extensions that can provide better recommendation capabilities. These extensions include, among others, the improved modeling of users and items, incorporation of the contextual information into the recommendation process, support for multicriteria ratings and provision of a more flexible and less intrusive recommendation process. The issues presented in this paper will advance the discussion in the recommender systems community about the next generation of recommendation technologies.

R. Forsati and M. Shamsfard, [8] proposed With the advent of online social networks, recommender systems have become crucial for the success of many online applications/services due to their significance

role in tailoring these applications to user-specific needs or preferences. Despite their increasing popularity, in general, recommender systems suffer from data sparsity and cold-start problems. To alleviate these issues, in recent years, there has been an upsurge of interest in exploiting social information such as trust relations among users along with the rating data to improve the performance of recommender systems. The main motivation for exploiting trust information in the recommendation process stems from the observation that the ideas exposed to and the choices we make are significantly influenced by our social context. However, in large user communities, in addition to trust relations, distrust relations also exist between users. For instance, in Epinions, the concepts of personal “web of trust” and personal “block list” allow users to categorize their friends based on the quality of reviews into trusted and distrusted friends, respectively. Hence, it will be interesting to incorporate this In this article, we have made progress towards making distrust information beneficial in the social recommendation problem. In particular, we have proposed a framework based on matrix factorization which is able to incorporate both trust and distrust relationships between users in a factorization algorithm. The potential distrust as side information to overcome data sparsity and cold-start problems in traditional recommender systems.

Jennifer, Golbeck [9] propose the social networks are growing in number and size, with hundreds of millions of user accounts among them. One added benefit of these networks is that they allow users to encode more information about their relationships than just stating who they know. In this work, particularly interested in trust relationships and how they can be used in designing interfaces. In this paper, present film trust, a website that uses trust in web based social networks to create predictive movie recommendations. Using the film trust system as a foundation, these recommendations are more accurate than other techniques when the user's opinions about a film are divergent from the average. This technique both as an application of social network analysis, as well as how it suggests other analyses that can be performed to help improve collaborative filtering algorithms of all types. Within the film trust website, trust in social networks has been used as the foundation for generating predictive movie recommendations. The accuracy of the trust-based predictive ratings in this system is significantly

better than the accuracy of a simple average of the ratings assigned to a movie. The trust system also outperforms the recommended ratings from a Person-correlation based recommender system.

S.Rendle [10] propose the collaborative filtering is the most popular approach to build recommender systems and has been successfully employed in many applications. However, it cannot make recommendations for so-called cold start users that have rated only a very small number of items. In addition, these methods do not know how they are in their recommendations. Trust-based recommendation methods assume the additional knowledge of a trust network among users and can better deal with cold start users, since users only need to be simply connected to the trust network. On the other hand, the sparsity of the user item ratings forces the trust-based approach to consider ratings of indirect neighbors that are only weakly trusted, which may decrease its precision. In order to good trade propose a random walk model combining the trust-based and the collaborative approach for recommendation. The random walk model allows us to and to measure of a recommendation. Performed an evaluation on the epinions dataset and compared model with existing trust-based and collaborative methods. Recommender systems are emerging as tools of choice to select the online information relevant to a given user. Collaborative is the most popular approach to building recommender systems and has been successfully employed in many applications. However, it cannot make recommendations for so-called cold start users that have rated only a very small number of items. Collaborative methods are rather vulnerable to attacks that insert fraudulent user into the database. Finally, these methods do not know how they are in their recommendations. Trust-based recommender systems can better deal with cold start users, since users only need to be simply connected to the trust network. The trust-based approach is also much more robust to fraudulent attacks.

H. Ma, H. Yang [11] propose the data sparsity, scalability and prediction quality have been recognized as the three most crucial challenges that every collaborative filtering algorithm or recommender system. Many existing approaches to recommender systems can neither handle very large datasets nor easily deal with users who have made very few ratings or even none at all. Moreover, traditional recommender systems assume that all the

users are independent and identically distributed; this assumption ignores the social interactions or connections among users. In view of the exponential growth of information generated by online social networks, social network analysis is becoming important for many Web applications. Following the intuition that a person's social network will affect personal behaviors on the Web, this paper proposes a factor analysis approach based on probabilistic matrix factorization to solve the data sparsity and poor prediction accuracy problems by employing both users' social network information and rating records. The complexity analysis indicates the approach can be applied to very large datasets since it scales linearly with the number of observations, performs much better than the state-of-the-art approaches, especially in the circumstance that users have made few or no ratings. In this paper, based on the intuition that a user's social network will affect this user's behaviors on the Web, present a novel social recommendation framework fusing a user-item rating matrix with the user's social network using probabilistic matrix factorization.

The out performs the other state-of-the-art collaborative filtering algorithms and the complexity analysis indicates it is scalable to very large datasets. Moreover, the data fusion method using probabilistic matrix factorization introduce in this paper is not only applicable to social recommendation, but also can be applied to other popular research topics, such as social search and many other tasks in information retrieval and data mining. In this paper, the inner product of two vectors to fit the observed data; this approach assumes that the observed data is a linear combination of several latent factors. Although we use the logistic function to constrain the inner product, a more natural and accurate extension for this assumption is to use a kernel representation for the two low dimensional vectors, or a Polynomial Kernel, which map the relations of two vectors into a nonlinear space, and thus would lead to an increase in the model's performance.

J. Zhu [12] propose the most critical challenge for the recommendation system is to achieve the high prediction quality on the large scale sparse data contributed by the users. In this paper, present a novel approach to the social recommendation problem, which takes the advantage of the graph laplacian regularization to capture the underlying social relationship among the users. Differently from the

previous approaches that are based on the conventional gradient descent optimization formulate the presented graph laplacian regularized social recommendation problem into a low-rank semi definite program, which is able to be efficiently solved by the quasi-Newton algorithm. The promising very effective and efficient for the social recommendation task. It is clear that our novel low-rank semi definite program approach to social recommendation is powerful and effective. It offers several distinct advantages over the conventional approaches. First, introduce the graph laplacian to effectively regularize the user-specific latent space and capture the underlying relationships among the different users. Second, the presented social recommendation with the graph laplacian regularization problem is directly formulated into the low-rank semi definite programming, which can be efficiently solved by the quasi-Newton algorithm. Finally, the mapping function for the normalization is carefully addressed formulation.

H. Fang and Y. Bao [13] Trust has been used to replace or complement rating based similarity in recommender systems, to improve the accuracy of rating prediction. However, people trusting each other may not always share similar preferences. In this paper, fill in this gap by decomposing the original single-aspect trust information into four general trust aspects, i.e. benevolence, integrity, competence and predictability and further employing the support vector regression technique to incorporate them into the probabilistic matrix factorization model for rating prediction in recommender systems presented trust-aware recommendation approach to mitigate the research gap between user similarity and trust concepts in recommender systems. Specifically first decomposed the original single-aspect trust information into four general trust aspects, i.e. benevolence, integrity, competence and predictability. Then incorporated these aspects into the probabilistic matrix factorization model for rating prediction with the support vector regression technique. Comparisons with four state-of-the-art approaches, PMF, SVD++, Social MF and Trust MF. Indicating that the more valuable trust information is derived for recommendation.

G. Guo [14] propose the Providing high quality recommendations is important for online systems to assist users who face a vast number of choices in making effective selection decisions. Collaborative

filtering is a widely accepted technique to provide recommendations based on ratings of similar users. But it suffers from several issues like data sparsity and cold start. To address these issues, in this paper, propose a simple but effective method, namely “Merge”, to incorporate social trust information (i.e. trusted neighbors explicitly specified by users) in providing recommendations. More specifically, ratings of a user’s trusted neighbors are merged to represent the preference of the user and to find similar other users for generating recommendations. Both accuracy and coverage recommendations. Aim is overcome the data sparsity and cold-start problems for recommender systems, proposed a simple but effective method to incorporate trusted neighbors that are directly specified by users. The ratings of trusted neighbors are merged to represent the preference of the active user, based on which we then find similar users and generate recommend items. Other methods both in accuracy and coverage. Also demonstrated that it is not necessary for our method to propagate trust since incorporating direct trusted neighbors works well enough. Furthermore, by tuning the similarity threshold, better performance can be achieved method.

Y. Koren [15] propose the as the net flix prize competition has demonstrated, matrix factorization models are superior to classic nearest-neighbor techniques for producing product recommendations, allowing the incorporation of additional information such as implicit feedback, temporal effects and confidence levels. Modern consumers are inundated with choices. Electronic retailers and content providers offer a huge selection of products, with unprecedented opportunities to meet a variety of special needs and tastes. Matching consumers with the most appropriate products is key to enhancing user satisfaction and loyalty. Therefore, more retailers have become interested in recommender systems, which analyze patterns of user interest in products to provide personalized recommendations that suit a user’s taste. Because good personalized recommendations can add another dimension to the user experience, e-commerce leaders like made recommender systems a salient part of their websites. Matrix factorization techniques have become a dominant methodology within collaborative filtering recommenders. Experience with datasets such as the net flix prize data has shown that they deliver accuracy superior to classical nearest-neighbor techniques. At the same time, they offer a compact

memory-efficient model that systems can learn relatively easily. What makes these techniques even more convenient is that models can integrate naturally many crucial aspects of the data, such as multiple forms of feedback, temporal dynamics and confidence levels.

H. Ma, I. King [16] propose an indispensable technique in the field of Information Filtering, Recommender System has been well studied and developed both in academia and in industry recently. However, most of current recommender systems suffer the following problems: (1) The large-scale and sparse data of the user-item matrix seriously affect the recommendation quality. As a result, most of the recommender systems cannot easily deal with users who have made very few ratings. (2) The traditional recommender systems assume that all the users are independent and identically distributed; this assumption ignores the connections among users, which is not consistent with the real world recommendations. Aiming at modeling recommender systems more accurately and realistically, propose a novel probabilistic factor analysis framework, which naturally fuses the users’ tastes and their trusted friends’ favors together. In this frame work, the term Social Trust Ensemble to represent the formulation of the social trust restrictions on the recommender systems. The complexity analysis indicates that approach can be applied to very large datasets since it scales linearly with the number of observations, while the experimental results show that our method performs better than the state-of-the- art approaches. This paper is motivated by the fact that a user’s trusted friends on the Web will affect this user’s online behavior. Based on the intuition that every user’s decisions on the Web should include both the user’s characteristics and the user’s trusted friends’ recommendations, propose a novel, effective and efficient probabilistic matrix factorization frame work for the recommender systems. Moreover, the method introduced in this paper by using probabilistic matrix factorization is not only working in trust-aware recommender systems, but also applicable to other popular research topics, such as social search, collaborative information retrieval and social data mining.

CONCLUSION

Trust SVD extends to SVD ++, using the explicit and implicit impact of rated projects by further combining

the explicit and implicit impact of trust and trust users on active user project predictions. Trust SVD to achieve better accuracy than other recommended technology methods. This problem is overcome by introducing a frequency-based algorithm to reduce the error rate and avoid language problems, thereby improving the accuracy of the recommendation.

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